
Chapter 6

Practical applications of neurocomputing

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ABSTRACT

Artificial neural net (ANN) models, or neural networks, connectionist models, parallel distributed processing models and neuromorphic systems are systems that are constructed to mimick some of the organisational principles of the human brain. Such systems have been studied in the past, aiming to achieve human-like performance in the recognition and classification of different patterns, for example image and speech recognition. There has been a recent revival in the field, caused by new neural network topologies and learning algorithms and current VLSI manufacturing technology. This paper provides a brief survey of the history of neurocomputing, followed by an outline of learning procedures, and finally focuses on practical applications and implementation of ANN models. Practical applications of neurocomputing with their promising results have stimulated scientists to search for new tools for handling difficult or unresolved problems. Approaching the doorstep of the 21st century we are facing a competitive market which must be provided with updated tools for managing highly demanding applications. Neural networks as artificial intelligence tools are expected to play a pioneering role and a promising tool for the year 2000.

1. MACHINE LEARNING

The main object of natural or artificial learning systems is to expand their knowledge in order to conform to the uncertainty and the unknown. The past experience of a learning system when properly used contributes to the improvement of its performance. It may therefore be suggested that learning is the automatic improvement of the performance of a system. When it comes to intelligence machine learning may be the key to machine intelligence just as human learning is the key to human intelligence.

One of the main drawbacks of classical computers is that they lack intelligence. They are instructed by means of a program of what to do, in a step-by-step manner through program statements. A task on a computer might be performed thousands of times, contributing nothing to the experience and learning of the task. In contrast, a human being doing something for the second time will usually do it better with added experience. Learning can thus be achieved through systematic training. Learning has played a decisive role in building Artificial Intelligence (AI), and a lot of theoretical work has been done by AI researchers for simulating the learning process.

There is disagreement in the AI community on whether or not intelligence must be simulated using the same procedures as humans do. Some researchers are goal-oriented and others are means-oriented. The former prefer the term "machine intel-

ligence" to "artificial intelligence" and believe that the goal is simply to simulate intelligent behavior on a computer, using any techniques that prove to be effective. The latter claim that if intelligence is simulated using procedures other than those that might be used by humans the term of AI cannot be applied (Mishkoff, (1)).

In our opinion, such debates cannot solve the AI problem. In order to develop a thinking computer, it is essential to define what intelligence is and how the brain works. A combination of the above two suggestions might lead to a more promising avenue. Otherwise, researchers will be disillusioned as they were in the 60's when the idea of AI was dropped since not enough was known on the "real" subject they were trying to simulate.

Human intelligence is indeed a difficult concept to define with great precision. If we cannot even agree on what constitutes human intelligence, how will we know when we have successfully achieved artificial intelligence. Human rationality has been debated since the beginning of mankind. Aristotle and Plato were among the first ones to divide human capabilities into those resulting from the physical body and to those of the rational mind. The functioning of the rational mind is believed to have a mechanistic nature. This view is the belief that the workings of the mind can be described in terms of the electrochemical functioning of the brain.

There is a general instinctive feeling that the workings of our mind can never be programmed into a machine and that no computer will ever have a mind of its own. We all hope however, to create a machine which will be capable of doing things in a way that appears to be intelligent. Alan Turing, in the 1930's, suggested that machine thinking has to be compared to human performance. Turing proposed to place a human being and a machine in one room, and another human, the interrogator, in a separate room. The interrogator may ask questions to either the human or the machine, referring to one as X and the other as Y. The interrogator, who is isolated from X and Y simply passes messages to them and evaluates their performance. As they respond to questions, X and Y compete to convince the interrogator that he/she is the human. If the machine achieved the same score as the human, then it passes the "Turing Test", and by this criterion can think. In practice, the result of this test would depend heavily on the humans involved as well as the machine (Tanimoto (2)).

In practice the problem of AI implementation has been temporarily overcome by introducing the expert system concept. Expert systems or otherwise known as knowledge-based systems are computer programs designed to emulate the reasoning process of an expert in his particular domain of expertise. The knowledge of the system consists of facts about the domain in question, and heuristics for applying those facts. Heuristics are rules of thumb which are used by the expert in real life practice for solving problems. Bruce Buchanan in Encyclopedia Britannica defines artificial intelligence as: *the branch of computer science that deals with ways of representing knowledge using symbols rather than numbers and with rules-of-thumb, or heuristic methods for processing information.*

Other tools or concepts which have been introduced together with expert systems in an effort to bridge the AI gap are symbolic processing, pattern matching, natural language processing, speech recognition, computer vision, intelligent computer-assisted instruction, automatic programming and planning, and decision support.

2. HISTORICAL SURVEY OF NEUROCOMPUTING

In 1943 Warren S. McCulloch and Walter Pitts (3) published the most influential paper in neurocomputing, entitled "A logical calculus of the ideas immanent in nervous

activity" in the Bulletin of Mathematical Biophysics. What is now well known as the "McCulloch-Pitts" neuron was first described in that paper. This neuron is a binary device, has a fixed threshold, and receives inputs from excitatory and inhibitory synapses.

Excitatory synapses had identical weights, whereas inhibitory synapses if active, turned the neuron off. There was a time quantum for integration of synaptic inputs, based loosely on the physiologically observed synaptic delay. The McCulloch-Pitts neuron functioned as follows: *during the time quantum, the neuron responded to the activity of its synapses which reflected the state of the presynaptic cells. If no inhibitory synapses were active, the neuron added its synaptic inputs and checked to see if the sum exceeded the threshold to fire, otherwise not to.*

Thus, the McCulloch-Pitts neuron functioned like a simple threshold logic. This "all-or-none" law of neuron activity, according to McCulloch and Pitts is sufficient to ensure that the activity of any neuron may be represented as a proposition. The network of connections between simple propositions can give rise to more complex propositions. The key issue of that paper was that any finite logical expression could be realised by McCulloch-Pitts neurons. According to Anderson and Rosenfeld (4), this was an exciting result since it showed that simple elements connected in a network could have immense computational power.

Defining Terms

Auto associative (memory) system or linear associator: the system stores information related to specific patterns repeatedly presented to it. When a similar pattern is applied to the system, the associated information is revealed. Degraded or incomplete inputs are tolerated by the system to give a correct response.

Back propagation: a learning algorithm for a multilayer network. Weights are adapted by propagating an error signal backwards, from the outputs to the inputs.

Connection: a pathway between processing elements. It links the processing elements into a network. It corresponds to the axons and synapses of the biological neuron.

Hidden layer: a layer of units (nodes) between the input and output layers. It provides additional computation power to the system.

Learning: the phase where new data is presented to the system, causing all or some of the weights to be modified.

Neuron: the structural and functional unit of the nervous system. It consists of the nerve cell body, an axon, one or more dendrites and the synapses. Electrical impulses are carried through the dendrites to the cell body, and then propagated away from the cell body through the axon. Impulses are transmitted to adjacent neurons through the synapses.

Perceptron: developed in 1958 by Frank Rosenblatt. A class of simple neuron like networks with only an input layer and an output layer. Perceptrons have no hidden layers.

Threshold: a minimum level, above which excitation begins.

Training: a process whereby a network learns to associate an input pattern with the correct output, class or result.

Weight: the strength of a connection expressed numerically. Processing elements receive input via interconnections, whereby each interconnection has a weight assigned to it. The sum of the weights, is input to the activation function, the output of which determines the state (intensity) of the processing element.

Donald O. Hebb (5) published his famous book "The Organisation of Behavior" in 1949, where for the first time he explicitly defined the physiological learning rule for synaptic modification that has since become known as the Hebb's synapse. According to Hebb (5): *when an axon of cell A is near enough to excite a cell B and repeatedly or persistently takes part in firing it, some growth process or metabolic change takes place in one or both cells such that A's efficiency, as one of the cells firing B, is increased.* The main theme of Hebb's book was what he called "cell assemblies". The basic issue was that there were interconnected self-reinforcing subsets of neurons that formed the representations of information in the nervous system. Individual cells might contribute to more than one assembly. Multiple cell assemblies could be active simultaneously, corresponding to tasks of varying complexity. The idea of distributed representation was assumed to be used in a way similar to the nervous system.

From the first days of the computer era John von Neumann (6), one of the pioneers of computer science and computer hardware design, supported the potential analogy between digital computers and the brain. Just before Neumann's death in 1957, in a set of notes for his book "The computer and the brain", the following issues were addressed: *i) the importance of memory in biological nervous systems (as in electronic ones) was discussed; and he mentioned that the exact means of storage is not known, which is still valid (Anderson and Rosenfeld (4)). He has suggested that memory capacity is of the order of 10^{20} bits (in 1986, Tom and Landones proposed that long-term memory is around 10^9 bits). Also, Neumann supported the rule of synaptic learning "strengthening by use", to form a permanent physical change in the brain, ii) Neumann outlined that neurons have very low precision, not more than a few bits, which affect the kinds of computations that the nervous system can do. Thus, only few operations can be carried out in succession before errors overwhelm the result, and iii) Neumann observed that the kinds of computations performed by the nervous system must be closely bound to its physical realisation.* Anderson and Rosenfeld (4) also support that this must be true.

Also, as early as 1946, John von Neumann, in collaboration with Arthur W. Burks and Herman H. Goldstein published the paper "Preliminary Discussion of the Logical Design of an Electronic Computing Instrument". This paper set the foundations of the concept of the stored program and introduced the idea of the program counter. It described a processor, the so-called von Neumann machine, that had to fetch successive instructions from memory. It also defined the bottleneck between the processor and memory that still survives today. A comparison between the neurocomputer and the von Neumann computer concepts is given in Table 2.1.

TABLE 2.1. A comparison of neural net and von Neumann computer concepts	
Neural Net Computer	von Neumann Computer
Non algorithmic	Algorithmic
Trained	Programmed with instructions
Adaptation or learning	Algorithmic modification only
Pursue multiple hypothesis in parallel	Pursue only one hypothesis at a time
May be fault tolerant	Non-fault tolerant
May process degraded or incomplete data	Not able to process incomplete data
Seeks answer by carrying out transformations, competition, etc	Seeks answer by following logical structure
Memory and processing elements are the same	Memory and processing elements are separate

Rosenblatt (7) introduced the perceptron, which was the first precisely specified computational neural network. The perceptron was a learning machine that was potentially capable of complex adaptive behavior. Although the first paper published by Rosenblatt is hard to follow, the machinery proposed by this paper is still in use today in different forms (Anderson and Rosenfeld (4)).

Rosenblatt felt that the appropriate way to view brain functioning was as a learning associator. The target was to couple classification responses to stimuli. He claimed that noise and randomness present in the nervous system were essential elements to the kinds of computations the brain is involved with. Perceptrons performed well at discriminating patterns in a "differentiated environment", but had limitations at handling arbitrary random patterns.

Rosenblatt assumed that the perceptron acted in some responses like a brain-damaged patient, being literal, inflexible, and unable to handle abstractions. To this date, according to Anderson and Rosenfeld (4), neural networks have the same drawbacks.

In 1960 Widrow and Hoff (8) proposed an adaptive system that performed learning abilities closely related to perceptrons. They called it an "adaptive neuron", which was a threshold-logic unit with variable connection strengths. The adaptive neuron computed a weighted sum of activities of the input, times the synaptic weight, plus a bias element. If the sum was greater than zero the output was assigned to +1, if it was equal to or less than zero the output was set to -1. They assumed that there was a "boss" who knew what the output should be for that input. The difference between the known (expected) output and the system calculated output formed the error signal. The synaptic weights were adjusted, and the sum recalculated, so the error signal became zero. Note that adjustments of synaptic weights were carried out even in cases where the classification was correct but not exactly equal to +1 or -1. This continued-learning was very important, in contrast to perceptron-learning where it took so long to learn, because synaptic weights were changed only when the gross classification was incorrect (Anderson and Rosenfeld (4)).

Widrow and Hoff (8) felt that the target is to reduce the square of the error signal to its smallest possible value. An error surface exists in the weight space, and the aim is to find where the minimum error surface is. This is quite difficult since the shape of the surface is not known, but examining the local topography of the error surface, directions of adjustments that will decrease the error the most can be determined. A gradient descent method is usually used to adjust the weights; that is change of weights to move the system down the error surface in the direction of the locally steepest descent. However, a serious problem with the gradient descent method is that in general the system might get trapped to local minima, ie. valleys in the error surface which are not the global minimum. Widrow and Hoff also showed that there is a simple quadratic error surface with only one global minimum.

Although Rosenblatt was well aware of some of the theoretical limitations of perceptrons, like the requirement for linear separability of data points as well as problems related if too much generalization was required, there was little appreciation for their magnitude. Minsky and Papert (9) analyzed the computational limitations of perceptrons exhaustively in their controversial book "Perceptrons", published in 1969. The most famous result in their book is the discussion of the geometrical predicate of connectedness (a figure drawn without lifting the pencil from the paper). Given a diameter-limited perceptron, it is possible to show that it cannot compute connectedness.

This book played an influential role in the history of neural networks because suddenly research on neural networks was unwanted, and most important, unfunded. In addition to this, as Anderson and Rosenfeld (4) comment, practical results with perceptrons failed to materialize. Small perceptron-based systems worked fine, larger ones tended not to work at all. Some of these findings were confirmed by Minsky and Papert as well.

In 1972, Teuvo Kohonen (10) and James Anderson (11), working independently published their work on associative memory, or what is well known as the "linear associator". There were several important assumptions in this model: continuous valued neural input multiplied by the synaptic weights, summed, with the output of the neuron being proportional to the sum. Thus, the model neuron became an analog integrator with continuous valued output. This meant that "Threshold Logic Units" of the kind used by Rosenblatt in the perceptron, and the analysis carried by Minsky and Papert in "Perceptrons" was inappropriate for the nervous system. According to Anderson and Rosenfeld (4) the major criticism of this class of models is their linearity. Although neurons are not linear for large signals, linear associative models proved to be very useful.

In 1982, Teuvo Kohonen (12) published the well known paper: "Self-organised formation of topologically correct feature maps". Similar to the brain organisation, where aspects of the sensory environment are represented in the form of two-dimensional maps, Kohonen attempted to construct an artificial system that can behave in similar fashion. In a topologically organised system, nearby units should respond similarly. The way this is achieved is discussed in the next section.

In 1982, Hopfield (13), (14) introduced the Hopfield net, which can be used as an associative memory or to solve optimisation problems. This net is most suitable when exact binary representations are possible. For continuous-valued inputs, conversion to binary values should be applied, being a drawback for the Hopfield net. A typical structure of a Hopfield net is shown in Fig. 2.1. It has N nodes containing hard limiting non linearities and binary inputs and outputs taking values of $+1$ and -1 . The output of each node is fed back to all other nodes. Initially weights are assigned. Then, an unknown pattern is applied, and the output of the net is forced to match the input, on successive iterations. The pattern specified by the node outputs after convergence is the net output.

Fig. 2.1 A typical Hopfield neural net that can be used as a content-addressable memory. Binary input is applied at time zero and the net iterates until convergence (node outputs do not change). The result is present at the output.

The Hopfield net has two limitations when used as a content addressable memory (Lippmann (15)): *i) the number of patterns that can be stored and accurately recalled is severely limited, and ii) a pattern will be unstable if it shares many bits in common with another pattern.*

Fukushima (16) proposed a multilayered neural network with strong self-organizing properties, which he called the "Cognitron" in 1975. Eight years later, he introduced a modification of the Cognitron, which he named the Neocognitron (Fukushima et al (17)).

The multilayer learning system proposed by Fukushima, Miyake and Ito modeled their system after the structure of the visual system given by Hubel and Weisel. They assumed a number of modules in series, with each module having a number of "S-cells", based in the properties of simple cells in the primary visual cortex and "C-cells". The S-cells responded to particular features in the dividing layer, and the C-cells responded to the features picked up by the S-cells.

The trained Neocognitron system is able to recognize handwritten numbers presented in any visual field location, even distorted. This system combined principles from physiology, engineering, and network theory, to devise a system that is applied in practice. Working through practical tasks to the completion of a system may be a promising scientific research strategy (Andreson and Rosenfield (4)).

In 1986, Gail Carpenter of Northeastern University and Stephen Grossberg of Boston University (18), in the development of their Adaptive Resonance Theory designed an ANN system which forms clusters of binary data and is trained without supervision. In this type of net, an example of which is given in Fig.2.2, matching scores are computed using feed forward connections and the maximum value enhanced using lateral inhibition among the output nodes. This net is described using non linear differential equations, includes extensive feedback, and has been shown to be stable (Carpenter and Grossberg (18)). Lippmann (15) comments that the Carpenter/Grossberg algorithm can perform well with perfect input patterns, but even a small amount of noise can cause problems.

In 1986, David E. Rumelhart, Geoffrey E. Hinton and Ronald J. Williams (19), (20) developed the well known "back propagation" algorithm for working with multilayer neural networks. Back propagation was discovered independently by Le Cum (21), and Parker (22). As it turned out, the algorithm had been described earlier as well, by Paul J. Werbos (23) in his Ph.D. thesis in 1974. The back propagation is a generalization of the Widrow-Hoff error correction rule. Rumelhart, Hinton and Williams developed the "generalized delta rule", which takes account of adjusting the strengths of synapses on internal or hidden units, based on the error at the output. A more detailed presentation of the back propagation algorithm is given in the following section. The back propagation is the most effective current learning algorithm for training multilayer systems.

Table 2.2 summarizes the most important discoveries in the field of artificial neural systems.

Fig. 2.2 The major components of the Carpenter/Grossberg net are shown. Binary input is presented at the input and when classification is complete only one output is high.

TABLE 2.2 Key discoveries in neurocomputing history

Discovery	Investigator	Year
Threshold logic devices	McCulloch-Pitts	1943
Hebbian learning	Hebb	1949
Perceptron	Rosenblatt	1958
MADALINE, least means squares algorithm	Widrow and Hoff	1960
Linear associator	Anderson and Kohonen	1972
Back propagation	Paul Werbos	1974
Cognitron	Fukushima	1975

Adaptive resonance	Grossberg	1978
Self-organising feature maps	Kohonen	1982
Hopfield nets	Hopfield	1982
Neocognitron	Fukushima	1983
Adaptive resonance theory	Carpenter and Grossberg	1986
Back propagation	Rumelhart, Hinton and Williams	1986

3. LEARNING AND NEURAL NETWORKS

The major goal of research on networks of neuron-like processing units is to discover efficient learning procedures that will enable these networks to construct complex internal representations of their environment (Rich (24)). Artificial neural networks are biologically inspired. A biological neuron consists of axons, dendrites, and synapses with excitatory and inhibitory inputs. An artificial neuron, implemented in hardware emulates the axon and dendrites of its biological counterpart with wires and emulates the synapses with resistors and weighted values. In essence, neural network models consist of processing elements which interact with each other, via interconnected topologies. The topologies are determined by a characteristic architecture, and a learning scheme such as supervised or unsupervised.

Further to the above, there are two basic reasons for investigating artificial neural networks. First, these networks resemble the brain much more closely than conventional computers. Even though there are many detailed differences between connectionist units and real neurons, a deeper understanding of the computational properties of connectionist networks may reveal principles that apply to a whole class of devices of this kind, including the brain. Second, connectionist networks are massively parallel, so any computations that can be performed efficiently with these networks can make good use of parallel hardware.

As stated above, learning is achieved through systematic training. Training a neural network is a matter of adjusting weights, either manually or automatically. Irrespective of weight adjustment, neural network learning can take place in one of three ways: supervised, unsupervised, or self-supervised.

In supervised learning, input and output data are supplied to the network in an effort to teach it to produce the desired output vector. In unsupervised learning, data is simply entered into the network without any human intervention. Learning is achieved through the formation of internal constructions that capture regularities in their input vectors without receiving any additional information. In self-supervised learning, the network monitors itself and corrects errors in the interpretation of data by feedback through the network. In all network learning methods, learning is achieved when the network achieves stability. After the initial weights are set (usually to small random values), data is entered into the network; this process causes it to pass through state changes and ultimately reach stability when the weight values that are associated with the processing elements, stop changing. Therefore, a neural network learns by adapting itself. This is accomplished through changes in the weights as the network gains experience. The learning rule, based on the methodology of learning adopted, is the very heart of a neural network. Of the numerous learning rules in use, the most

well known are the Hebb's rule and the delta rule (Lawrence (25)). Nearly all other rules are variations of these two. Out of the many types of neural networks which are listed in the literature (Hinton (26), Lippmann (15) and Lawrence (25)), we will concentrate on the supervised back propagation (Rumelhart et al (19), (20)), and the unsupervised self-organizing feature maps algorithm of Kohonen (12), (27).

3.1 BACK PROPAGATION - SUPERVISED LEARNING

Fig. 3.1 A three-layer perceptron with 5 continuous valued inputs, 3 units (nodes) in first hidden layer, 4 units in second hidden layer, and 3 outputs.

The back propagation algorithm is the most popular learning paradigm implemented today to train multilayer nets. A multilayer feed forward network is illustrated in Fig. 3.1. This system is trained using the generalized delta rule. The aim of this feed-forward network is to feed the error signal back to the network. The objective is to prevent the same error from happening again by appropriately altering the weights. The back propagation is useful because it provides the mathematical explanation for the dynamics of the learning process. It is also very consistent and reliable in the kinds of applications that can currently be built, either with continuous or binary value inputs. A serious limitation, however is the size of the network. Despite its impressive performance on relatively small problems, it is inadequate in its current form for large tasks. Our efforts are currently concentrated in finding ways for optimising the back propagation technique and make it problem and size adaptive.

3.2 KOHONEN - UNSUPERVISED LEARNING

The unsupervised feed-forward model of self-organization developed by Kohonen (12), (27) is a one or two dimensional array of neuron-like logic units with lateral

connections between neighboring neurons. An example of this system is given in Fig. 3.2. The system modifies itself so that nearby neurons respond similarly. The neuron whose weight vector generates the largest dot product with the input vector is the winner and is permitted to output. In this model not only the weights of the winner but also those of its nearest neighbor are adjusted. One of the problems with this type of learning is that there is a possibility that a neuron will never "win", or that one will almost always "win". This can be

avoided by taking the particular neuron out of the competition process for a while until other neurons get the chance to "win". Other practical difficulties in using the Kohonen maps is the non existence of a way in choosing the size of the output grid and the initial value of gain. These factors are left entirely to the investigator who has to base his choices entirely on heuristic and non algorithmic procedures.

Fig. 3.2 Two dimensional array of output nodes used to form the Kohonen feature maps. Every input is connected to every output via a variable connection weight. Topological neighborhoods ($NE_j(t)$) at different times are shown. The neighborhood starts large and slowly decreases over time. In this figure $0 < t_1 < t_2$.

4. NEURAL NETWORK APPLICATIONS

A number of practical neural network applications as they have been developed for various disciplines are discussed. Our team introduced the application of artificial neural net systems in clinical electromyography; also, work has been initiated in the area of weather forecasting.

4.1 NAVLAB road tracker

David S. Touretzky and Dean A. Pomerleau (28) at Carnegie Mellon University are working in automatic vehicle navigation using neural networks. The target of ALVINN (autonomous land vehicle in a neural network) is to drive the NAVLAB vehicle along a winding road. ALVINN receives inputs from: *i) 30 x 32 pixel image from a video camera mounted on the roof of the vehicle, and ii) 8 x 32 pixel image from a laser range finder.* The two inputs are connected to a single layer of hidden units, which in turn are connected to the output units. Each node at the output layer represents the direction in which the vehicle should travel to lead towards the center of the road. There are 45 output units in the ALVINN system with the middle node representing "travel straight ahead", while units to the left and right of center represent successively sharper left and right turns. Training of ALVINN is a very difficult task; once trained, it can accurately drive the NAVLAB vehicle at about 3.5 miles per hour along a path of varied scenery. It should be mentioned, that this speed is twice as fast as that achieved by non neural network algorithms running the NAVLAB vehicle.

4.2 NETTALK: a neural network that learns to read aloud

Sejnowski and Rosenberg (29) have shown that a neural network with one hidden layer can be trained to pronounce English letters surprisingly well. The proposed ANN model has 309 units and 18629 connections. The number of output units is 26, number of hidden units 80 and number of input units 7 x 29. A window seven letters wide is slid over the text, and the network pronounces the middle letter. The system requires a preprocessor to identify characters, and a postprocessor to turn phonemes into sound. Sejnowski and Rosenberg (29) used the 1000 most common English words to study the performance of the network. The best performance achieved was 98% best guesses, but with 120 hidden units. This network was tested on a randomized dictionary of 20012 words. Without learning, the average performance was 77% best guesses and 28% perfect matches. After 5 training cycles, the system performance increased to 90% best guesses and 48% perfect matches.

4.3 THE "NEURAL" PHONETIC TYPEWRITER

Teuvo Kohonen (30), (31) used the self-organizing algorithm to implement a neural network system which is able to transcribe text of unlimited dictation of the Finnish and Japanese languages. Maximum accuracy achieved was 90% and most of the errors that occurred were caused by coarticulation effects. By using no language model, Kohonen has furtherly implemented a phonetic typewriter of unlimited text based on this system. The microphone signal was preprocessed in the following path: *i) low-pass filtered at 5.3KHz, ii) passed through a 12 bit A/D converter with 13.02KHz sampling rate, iii) 256 point FFT every 9.83ms using Hamming window, iv) logarithmization and smoothing of the power spectrum, and v) placing 15 components into a spectral vector in the frequency range of 200Hz to 5KHz.*

A phoneme map was the simplest type of phonotopic map formed by self-organization. There are 21 phonemes in Finnish, for the representation of which short-time spectra were evaluated every 9.83 ms, as mentioned above. All the phonemes were presented to the algorithm in the order of their utterance. After adaptation, the map was calibrated using known phonemes. Any sequence of responses for utterances of speech segments can be visualized as a trajectory on the map.

4.4 CLASSIFICATION OF SONAR TARGETS USING A MASSIVELY PARALLEL NETWORK

Paul Gorman and Terrence Sejnowski (32) applied neural networks for the classification of sonar returns from two undersea targets, a cylinder and a rock. Sonar models with one hidden layer achieved 100% correct classification of a training set of 104 returns. For testing the performance of the proposed models, 104 sonar returns not presented to the network during training were applied. Accuracy obtained during testing was 90.4%. Gorman and Sejnowski concluded their study by mentioning that for a three layer network, performance obtained was better than trained human listeners.

4.5 NETEMG: Artificial neural networks in electromyography

Recent advances in quantitative electromyography (EMG) have demonstrated the importance of quantification in the neurophysiological diagnosis of neuromuscular diseases. Artificial neural networks were considered by Schizas et al. (33), (34) and Pattichis et al. (35) as possible candidates for handling the processing and classification of EMG data.

Motor unit action potential (MUAPs) were recorded from the biceps muscle of normal subjects and of patients suffering with motor neuron disease (MND) and myopathies. An automatic pattern recognition algorithm based on the MUAP features developed by Pattichis et al. (35), were applied and the parameters measured were: amplitude, phases, duration, area, spike duration, and spike area. MUAP findings were applied to models trained to diagnose normals, MND and myopathic patients. The back propagation algorithm was utilised to train three layer perceptron neural net models. A number of models were also investigated using the Kohonen unsupervised learning algorithm.

Twenty-seven subjects were used in the above studies; seventeen for training and ten for evaluating the ANN models. Diagnostic yield for both supervised and unsupervised models was in the range of 70-80%. Table 4.1 shows four typical models which were examined with supervised learning. ANN architecture denotes number of inputs, number of nodes in first hidden layer, number of nodes in second hidden layer and number of nodes in the output layer. Epoch represents the number of training cycles. TSS is defined as the sum of the squared difference between the derived and the expected output for all cases in an epoch. TS% and ES% denote the percentage level of success during training and evaluation respectively.

A Kohonen feature map obtained without supervision to classify EMG data is given in Fig. 4.1. This figure shows the mappings of normals, MND and myopathic subjects.

Model	ANN Architecture	Epochs	TSS	Diagnostic Yield	
				TS%	ES%
1	12-40-120-3	822	0.79	100	70
2	12-120-200-3	321	0.89	100	80
3	120-360-240-3	63	0.89	100	80
4	120-360-480-3	46	0.89	100	70

Fig. 4.1 EMG feature maps for normals (1), MND (2), and myopathic (3) subjects

4.6 AEOLOS: a weather forecasting system

One of Widrow's early neural-network applications dated back to 1963 was that of a simple weather forecasting system. When this system was fed with samples of yesterday's pressure and today's weather, it could forecast tomorrow's weather. Unfortunately we haven't been able to trace any more information about this application.

A similar problem to the above is the forecasting of the minimum temperature of the following day given certain factors which are measured during the previous day. Current methods for solving this problem are mainly statistical and they were found to be inadequate. A neural network pilot study for solving the weather forecasting problem using real data has been initiated by our team in collaboration with members of the Meteorological Services.

The whole study of the "minimum temperature forecasting" problem was divided into four stages: *i) preparation of the data and setting up the models, ii) training of the neural network using previous years known data, iii) evaluation of the various models with data not used in the training stage, and iv) application of the models in a real life environment.*

During stage (i) the factors which possibly affect the minimum temperature provided by the meteorological services were studied. It has been suggested by the weather experts that these factors are: day length, total cloud, wind speed, wind direction, visibility, present weather condition, QFE (atmospheric pressure), dry bulb, wet bulb, total amount of cloud, and current day minimum temperature. Some

of these factors are measured in non-linear scales or they are coded. An effort was made to transform these parameters to a consistent scale.

All of the above factors, with the exception of day length and current day minimum temperature are measured every three hours. Beginning at 06.00am the total number of readings is 38 (4 sets of 9 readings + day length + current day minimum temperature). At 09.00am the total number of readings is 47, and at 06.00pm these readings go up to 74. It would have been nice if one could forecast the minimum temperature as soon as a set of readings is recorded, ie. at 06.00am, 09.00am, 12.00 noon, etc.

The back propagation training algorithm was applied in five different models as shown in Table 4.2.

Model	Forecasting time	Set of Readings	Number of Inputs	Number of outputs
1	06.00	4	38	40
2	09.00	5	47	40
3	12.00	6	56	40
4	15.00	7	65	40
5	18.00	8	74	40

At the input all the available readings are presented as a vector. The output is a 40 element vector. Minimum and maximum temperatures of the left most and right most output nodes are -5°C and 15°C respectively. Each output node has an accuracy of 0.5°C .

During stage (ii) various models with different architectures were trained. Real data of nearly three months was made available to us by the Metereological Services. About a third of this data selected at random was kept for evaluation and the rest was used for training the various models. Table 4.3 shows some of the results obtained for various architectures, and Fig.4.2 gives their corresponding learning curves.

Fig. 4.2 Learning curves of weather forecasting models of Table 4.3.

This table also shows the evaluation results of stage (iii). During stage (iii) the data which did not participate in training were presented at the input of the trained models and the derived results were compared to the expected. Stage (iv) has not been examined yet since the preliminary results eventhough promising do not allow these models to be applied in practice. It is estimated that at least one year's data is required

to train the system. Currently an effort is made to prepare a complete training set and further investigate different models and architectures for finding the optimum.

Model	Architecture	Epochs	TSS	Forecasting Yield	
				TS%	ES%
1	42-80-160-40	585	21.9	56	48
2	66-150-300-40	1390	1.2	98	52
3	58-120-240-40	2855	3.1	94	44

It is expected that when more data is used for training the models, this system will become more reliable and with higher forecasting yield. It is anticipated that due to the high computational needs of the back propagation algorithm work has to be done towards optimizing the algorithm or otherwise consider using another algorithm.

5. IMPLEMENTATION

Hardware implementation of neural networks aims to efficiently and cost effectively process neural network problems. Neural networks of different architectures and learning laws have been presented causing the hardware structure of ANN systems to take different forms.

In the early days of the neural network era Frank Rosenblatt created the electro-mechanical perceptron. This device had 512 connections, 8 processing elements and speedwise it could handle 10^3 connections per second. The perceptron was used for typed-character recognition, limited to difference in scale, translation and distortion.

In 1960-62 Bernard Widrow built the MADALINE (multiple adaptive linear elements) at Stanford University. The Madaline was firstly an electrochemical device, and later on became electronic. The MADALINE has been in commercial use for more than 20 years. Its common use is in adaptive equalizers (echo cancellers) in telephone lines, as well as in adaptive modems.

Recent powerful electronic implementations of ANN systems include the Delta floating-point processor and Anza plus by Science Applications International Corporation and Hecht-Nielsen Neurocomputer Corporation respectively (Tazelaar (36)). These neurocomputers are able to process up to 1 million elements and handle the calculations of up to 1 million connections per second. Cost for these coprocessor cards varies from \$10000 to \$25000.

Also electrooptical and optical neural networks have been implemented by Demetri Psaltis at the California Institute of Technology in 1984 and Dana Anderson at the University of Colorado in 1986 respectively (Hecht-Nielsen (37)). In electrooptical neurocomputers, optical signals link electronic processing elements, whereas in optical neurocomputers, light signals link optical processing elements made out of some non linear optical material. The first one could handle 10^3 connections, at a speed of 10^5 connections per second. The second one could handle 2×10^6 connections at a speed of 2×10^7 connections per second.

Although neurocomputer coprocessor cards to simulate neural networks are now commercially available, they are still orders of magnitude slower than what can be achieved by directly fabricating networks with hardware. The most promising approach for implementing electronic neural nets is to fabricate special-purpose VLSI (very-large-scale-integration) chips. Today's integration density, allows for a large number of simple processors to be packed on a single chip, together with the necessary connections. Several groups such as Graf et al. (38) are currently working on neural systems based on VLSI technology.

In summer 1989, Intel announced the manufacturing of an Electronic Trainable Artificial Neural Network (ETANN) chip that will be capable of up to 2 billion multiplies and accumulates per second (Erickson (39)). To put the chip to work Mark Holler, the Director of the project and his ten member team, have built a prototype ETANN-based board that plugs into the PC-AT bus.

The creators of BrainMaker, a successful and cheap neural net simulation package for PCs, are working in the development of software tools for the ETANN chip. Also, Intel is investigating the possibility of putting a version of the ETANN board into an i860-based system that can achieve 33 billion connections per second.

Recently, Sharp introduced a neural network image processor chipset that simulates human vision (Erickson (39)). Sharp claims that this chip can support PC applications at speeds up to 700 MIPS (million integer instructions per second).

There are a number of software packages nowadays on the market that allow the design of neural network systems of various complexities (Tazelaar (36), Hecht-Nielsen (37)). Most of these packages run under MS-DOS, with some of them supporting VAX-VMS and Unix operating systems.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The study of neural networks has a long history which can be traced back in the 1940s to the work of McCulloch and Pitts, to the era of perceptrons with Rosenblatt in the 1950s and to Widrow and Hoff in the beginning of the 1960s.

The field was criticised for its limitations in the 1960s by Minsky and Papert in their book "Perceptrons". Revival in the field occurred in the 1970s and 1980s with the work of Grossberg, Carpenter, Kohonen, Hopfield, Rumelhart, Hinton and Williams. Progress in this area has been achieved based on research efforts across many disciplines including psychology, neurobiology, neurophysiology, mathematics, engineering, computer science and cognitive psychology.

This paper discusses two of the most widely used learning algorithms, ie. the back propagation algorithm for supervised learning and the Kohonen self-organizing feature maps for unsupervised learning. Both algorithms handle continuous valued inputs.

Practical applications of neural nets in image processing, control, speech, digital signal processing (sonar waves), clinical electromyography and weather forecasting currently investigated are presented. Results show the capacity as well as the limitations of the neural net systems in the real world environment.

The greatest potential of ANNs remains in hardware, specifically high speed processing that could be achieved through massively parallel VLSI implementations. Also software for neural net systems currently given only minor attention, needs more emphasis and development to provide performance required for practical applications. Anderson and Rosenfeld (4) mention that software for ANNs will be a most difficult task to handle.

This rapidly developing field has already presented some promising results which will become clearer only with more real-world applications (Shriver (40)). Although it might be too optimistic to predict that by the year 2000 neural-network technology will account for half the total revenues of the robotics and computer markets (Obermeier and Barron (41)).

It is important to point out that neurocomputing is by no means a replacement for software development; at least not in the near future. Neurocomputing is a technology in its infancy and the techniques currently available are limited in their capabilities and ranges of applicability.

Several questions remain unanswered:

1. Are specific neural net models more appropriate for specific data sets applied to than others, and how can supervised and unsupervised learning be combined in such systems?

2. How does the nature of the data set affect the structure of models (number of hidden layers, number of nodes, etc.)?

3. What hardware is best suitable for particular models and what software can be combined with these for maximum performance?

4. How can neural net systems behave more naturally, ie. generalizing, guessing or working with noisy and partially rule-based systems? Also at what level and how will neural computers be allowed to make mistakes, thus helping in the "generalization" process?

5. How will new findings in neuroscience help neural net engineers to devise better and faster learning algorithms?

6. Finally, how do neural network systems compare to classical pattern recognition systems?

The competitive world of automation we are living in needs to be supported with intelligent machine systems. Hopefully, these tools will help scientists to tackle problems that otherwise would have remained unresolved, or practically difficult to examine. Artificial neural systems are expected to play an influential role in the 21st century.

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